

ANALYSIS OF POLICY IMPLEMENTATION OF TYPE A GAMBUT BARAKAT KILOMETER 17 TERMINAL OPERATION, BANJAR DISTRICT, KALIMANTAN SELATAN PROVINCE, INDONESIA

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Abstract:

The decision of the Minister of Transportation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 132 PM is a regulation that regulates the operation of the terminal covering 3 things, namely planning, operation, and supervision. The Type A Gambut Barakat Terminal which has been completed in 2014 is intended for AKAP to operate in this type A terminal. Before this type A Gambut Barakat terminal was built AKAP operates in type B terminal km 6 Banjarmasin City. In this study type A Gambut Barakat terminal was chosen as the object of research in looking at the implementation of the operation policy. The research method used is a descriptive qualitative case study. The speakers in this study were 4 people, namely KORSATPEL Terminal type A Gambut Barakat km 17, the Chief of UPTD terminal type B km 6 Banjarmasin, the City Transport entrepreneurs, and Organda km 6 General Director. The focus of this research was the accompanying instruments implementation, namely the interests that are affected, the types of benefits obtained, the degree of change to be achieved, the location of decision making, program implementers, resources, power, interests and strategies of actors, characteristics of the ruling institution, compliance and responsiveness. As well as factors that become obstacles in the implementation of the operation of the type A terminal. Data analysis techniques carried out by researchers are by collecting data obtained from interviews, direct observation, and literature. From the findings of the data and research analysis, the implementation of the policy on the operation of the type A Gambut Barakat terminal is still not effective. Constraints faced in the implementation include the unavailability of AKAP moving from the type B km 6 terminal in South Kalimantan province to the type A Gambut Barakat terminal, less assertive action from the policy implementor, and AKAP feels that it does not benefit but instead loses when moving to the type A Gambut Barakat terminal.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Research Background

The more developed the times, human needs will be more and more diverse. Each stage of development must lead to ongoing demands in the provision of facilities and infrastructure for an effective and efficient transportation system so that the movement can take place safely, comfortably, quickly and smoothly in terms of cost and time for the continuity and guarantee of the implementation of the development. According to Miro (1997), the city transportation system can be interpreted as a unit consisting of parts that support each other and work together in the procurement of transportation that serves urban and rural areas. The components referred to from the transportation system are one of them is a terminal.

That Road Traffic and Transport has a very important role in efforts to support national development and integration as part of efforts to advance public welfare as mandated by the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia. Road traffic and transportation are part of the national transportation system must be developed and managed to realize security, safety, traffic order and order to support economic development and regional development.

Road Traffic and Transportation is an integrated system consisting of Traffic, Road Transportation, Road Traffic and Transportation Networks, Road Traffic and Transportation Infrastructure, Vehicles, Drivers, Road Users, and their management.

The terminal is the meeting point in the system of road transportation networks which also functions as a public service, namely as a place for boarding passengers, for loading and unloading goods and arranging arrivals and departures of public vehicles with the intention that each public transport starts and ends the trip at the terminal. The terminal as a public facility is also one of the assets of the local government, which provides a return value from the retribution to the regions in the form of local revenue. The public transport terminal is the transportation node and drop-out point, as a public service, in the form of public vehicles raising and lowering passengers, loading and unloading goods or people, and places where passengers move both within and between modes of transportation due to human activities that move from one place to another.

In-Law Number 22 of 2009 concerning Road Traffic and Transportation, dividing terminals into three types, as follows:

- 1) Type A passenger terminal serves public vehicles for Inter-Provincial City Transportation (AKAP), transportation of boundary traffic between countries,
- 2) 2 Type B passenger terminal which serves public vehicles for Inter-City Transportation in the Province (AKDP), city transportation (Angkot) and rural transportation (Angdes),

- 3) The type C passenger terminal serves public vehicles for urban transportation and rural transportation.

Type A passenger terminal that was completed in 2014 located on Jalan Ahmad Yani Km. 17 Gambut Subdistrict, Banjar Regency, South Kalimantan Province. The construction of this terminal costs up to tens of billions of rupees, more precisely 86 billion rupiahs, with details, 22 billion rupiah from central government support, for physical development, and 52 billion rupiahs from Banjar district government for land acquisition and making access roads. Besides, the funds are also supported by the South Kalimantan provincial government, which is 8 billion rupiahs for the construction of main roads and road lines (Radar Banjar; 9/9/2016). But until now the terminal that spends a lot of funds and long enough time is still quiet with terminal activities in general, such as the existence of Inter-Province City Transportation (AKAP), Angkot, Angdes, traders and passengers, there are only officers on guard at the terminal.

This is because of business people such as the AKAP Entrepreneurs who do not want to move from kilometer 6 terminal to kilometer 17 terminal. This matter is complicated by the support of In-Province City Transportation (AKDP) incorporated in Organda (Land Transport Organization), as well as traders who also support the AKAP that does not want to move to Terminal Type A km 17 in Banjar Regency for a number of reasons, including the distance of the terminal far from the city center which would make it difficult for passengers to go to the terminal. from the city of Banjarmasin to outside the area, with a long-distance terminal, most passengers will take other alternatives to travel between cities by using travel (black plate transportation).

The cost is almost the same, even cheaper than having to go to the kilometer 17 terminal in Banjar Regency, it will make it difficult for Angkot and Angdes to get passengers because the AKAP passengers are too far down, and fewer passengers mean less economic activity in km 6 terminal Banjarmasin. Besides, the presence of online taxis also affects the interests of the terminal to the terminal. Whereas in the legislation it is stipulated that terminals that may serve for AKAP are only typed A terminals, type B terminals for serving City Transportation in the Province. This condition is very contrary to the laws and regulations.

Actually, in the government's efforts to operate the type A km 17 terminal, Gambut Barakat, several trials were carried out and the first trial was conducted on March 14, 2013, for 14 days, then the trial was conducted again on May 20, 2015. The government conducted the trial not explained means lowering passengers in terminal km 17 but testing in terms of recognition, such as the location of entry, dropping and raising passengers, where to buy tickets, etc. But in fact, until now type A terminals in Banjar Regency are still not operational or quiet from traders, drivers, transportation and passengers, and AKAP are still active on type B km 6 terminal in South Kalimantan.

1.2 Problem Formulation

Departing from this phenomenon, the formulation of the problem for this study is as follows:

- 1) How is the implementation of the operation policy for Type A km 17 Gambut Barakat terminal in Banjar Regency?
- 2) What factors are constraints on the Implementation of Type A km 17 Gambut Barakat Terminal Operation Policies?

2. Methods

This research is included in the type of qualitative descriptive research to provide an overall picture of the background of the problem situation and the position of social interaction or current problems, as well as the interaction between the environment of certain social units that are objective. This research was carried out at the Type A Gambut Barakat, kilometer 17, Gambut District, Banjar Regency, South Kalimantan. The selection of research locations is based on consideration of the suitability of the substance of the problem in this study and also the consideration of data entry for people, programs, structures, and interactions according to needs. The purposive sampling method is used as a method in selecting informants. Namely, the informant was deliberately chosen by the author based on certain considerations such as the level of knowledge of the issue and case information in a comprehensive manner concerning the focus of research on the Operation Implementation of Type A Gambut Barakat Terminal. The author uses semi-structured interview techniques, namely questions and answer directly with informants to get clear, accurate and in-depth data. This research instrument uses interview guides, observation guidelines (sign system), and documentation. The technique used in this study is the qualitative analysis technique of Miles and Huberman.

3. Results

The following is the analysis of the advantages and disadvantages between the two terminals.

Type B km 6 Banjarmasin Terminal	
Advantages	Disadvantages
Located within the city of Banjarmasin and easily accessible to trade centers.	The location of the land is only 1.5 ha so it does not meet the requirements for the location of type A terminals which should be 3 Ha, while land acquisition for additional locations requires a long time and costs are very high.
In the form of type B terminals that have been operated and functioned as type A terminals so that road paving is no longer needed.	Access terminal exit/entry into one with public roads, namely public roads in the middle of the terminal.

Close to the Banjarmasin trisakti port.	Very close or side by side with residential areas.
City transportation taxis are available.	The existence of shophouses in a terminal location managed by a third party
Type A km 17 Gambut Barakat Terminal	
There is land readiness by the requirements of the Type A terminal area of 4 Ha and already has a Land Rights Certificate and an additional 5 Ha of grant land as terminal support land so that it is 9 Ha.	The absence of road hardening
The terminal location is at the road node point between the provinces of South Kalimantan, East Kalimantan, and Central Kalimantan.	Located on peat so it requires backfill.
Approval/recommendation has been obtained from the DPRD of the Province of South Kalimantan with Letter No: 162/867/DPRD dated 18 December 2006.	
There are the ability and willingness of the Banjar Regency Government to do hardening and paving roads that are paid for from the Regional Budget.	
The location of the terminal is not located near the residential area.	
Once designated as the location of type A passenger terminals based on Decree of the Minister of Transportation, in this case, the Director-General of Land Transportation Number: SK.126/AJ.107/DRDJD/98 dated 30 June 1998.	
Distance to Syamsudin Noor Airport as far as 8 Km.	
Distance to the city of Banjarmasin as far as 11 Km and has been available passenger transportation route Banjarmasin - Gambut.	
Road access to the terminal is available 40 meters wide	
There is support from employers and drivers of public passenger transportation.	
The land for the terminal location is peatland in the form of shrubs and not productive agricultural land.	

3. Discussion

Based on Grindle's theory of the influence of Policy Implementation with two components, namely content of the policy and implementation environment (context of implementation) and also the results of interviews with several informants at the time of observation and research, the discussion is as follows:

3.1 Contents of Policy

According to Grindle's theory, the contents of the policy have 6 elements, namely:

First, interests that influence, various interests that influence policy. In observation there are interests of PO owners and drivers, Organda km 6 Terminal, type B km 6 terminal officers, Type A Gambut Barakat terminal officers, and AKAP

passengers. Which each actor has their interests that are mutually contradictory so that the implementation of this operational policy can not be implemented properly.

Second, the benefits received will affect the success of this implementation process. In the researcher's observation, it was found that type A Barakat terminal KORSATPEL stated that there were many benefits obtained by the construction of Type A Gambut Barakat terminal, while the object of implementation, in this case, the PO owner and driver felt that no benefits were received.

Third, the degree of change that might result from policies implemented. Policies that are planned to achieve long-term goals will find difficulties compared to policies that have a beneficial effect. For passengers, the government rules only and in its implementation still considers the community as AKAP service users. Assume the PO owner and driver that the purpose of operating this type A terminal for passengers is not for us drivers and owners of POs. PO owners and drivers are reluctant because they do not benefit directly from this policy whereas according to KORSATPEL type A terminals with land area and rest facilities for AKAP are more value for this type A terminal. However, the presence of online-based transportation in big cities is an issue for Angdes and angkot because they get competitors and will influence the interest of the community to the terminal, but on the other hand, it makes it easy for the community because it is picked up and delivered to the destination.

Fourth, the location of decision making. The increasing number of decision making will increasingly complicate the implementation of its policies. At the beginning of the planning for the construction of the type A terminal Barakat has gone through technical studies and feasibility tests but in reality the stakeholders, in this case, the AKAP owners feel that from the initial stage to being operated this type A terminal is not involved. They think there is something wrong, why built there did not enlarge the existing terminal.

Fifth, the implementation process is not only concerned with the behavior of administrative bodies responsible for implementing the program but also for the network of political, economic, and social forces that influence the policy objectives of either negative or positive ones. To operate the type A Gambut Barakat terminal several simulations have been carried out for introduction, and officers have been on guard at the entrance of the terminal but in reality, there are no obedient buses to operate in the type A terminal but still in the area terminal type B.

Sixth, the resources used. Resources consist of human resources and financial resources, in this case, the facilities. With the presence of the type A Gambut Barakat terminal officer, it is expected that guarding the operation of the terminal and facilities in the terminal will be the opposite. AKAP's reluctance to move has caused type A Gambut Barakat terminal to not operate properly.

3.2 Context of Implementation

First, the power, interests, strategies of the actors involved by the actors with their interests give rise to various influences on the operation of the type A Gambut Barakat

terminal. The recognition of AKAP passengers is a bit heavy because the transfer of terminals means that they will add costs to terminal 17. AKAP owners have an interest in how they are going forward if they operate in a new terminal. KORSATPEL with the interest that the type A terminal can operate, the UPTD terminal 6 will support and carry out tasks according to the central instructions. The interests that do not meet the meeting point so that the operation of type A Gambut Barakat terminal is not good.

Second, characteristics of the ruling institution, the authority is given by the Ministry of Transportation, in this case, the BPTD staff in the area of 15 in the Province of South Kalimantan in terms of terminal operations are still facing obstacles. But it does not rule out the possibility of decisive action or sanctions will be given if AKAP is not obedient and moves to the type A Gambut Barakat terminal. So that the implementor can act decisively, decisively in the sense for

Third, compliance and responsiveness, compliance is one of the important components in efforts to achieve policy objectives. Compliance, in this case, is the compliance of the implementation object that is felt to be still low so that AKAP owners are still operating in type B terminals that should have moved to Type A Gambut Barakat terminal which has long been completed and several attempts to operate the terminal.

4. Conclusion

4.1 Implementation

This type A km 17 Gambut Barakat terminal has gone through the planning stage until the construction is completed then the officer has been placed in the terminal, but at the implementation stage until the supervision cannot be carried out because PO owners and AKAP drivers do not want to move from km 6 Banjarmasin Terminal to km 17 Gambut Barakat terminal. Between the executor of the policy and the subject of policy, implementation did not meet the meeting point so that until now there has not been a solution.

This shows that the implementation of the type A km 17 Gambut Barakat terminal has not been successful as to how far the interests of the target group are contained in the contents of the policy. The fact is that there are so many interests of each party that it is difficult to find a solution. Besides, the policies that have been made according to the implementor are already the best decisions, while according to the object of the implementation of the policy it harms them. This results in changes that cannot be achieved because of the refusal to follow the rules. The lack of assertiveness of program implementers in terms of giving sanctions to transports that do not follow the rules adds to the complexity of the problem. Since 2014, the development of the type A km 17 Gambut Barakat terminal has not been operated until now, even though various programs such as simulations in the context of introduction, officers on guard at the terminal, and public facilities are useful for passengers, traders or businessmen, and drivers.

4.2 Constraints

Type A km 17 Gambut Barakat Terminal has not yet been operational because AKAP is not compliant with regulations that should operate in the type A Gambut Barakat terminal. The many habits that have been changed in the operation of this terminal have arisen many interests and demands that have not been fulfilled by all so that it is still difficult to implement the terminal's operational policies. There has not been a direct benefit for AKAP when it is transferred from the old terminal to the new terminal. The less assertive action was shown by the implementor of the policy in this case the KORSATPEL type A Gambut Barakat terminal along with implementing members even though financial resources were adequate. Besides, there is support from ORGANDA km 6 Banjarmasin terminal to remain in the area of type B terminals which indirectly also benefit from this.

5. Recommendations

Based on these conclusions, suggestions can be developed as follows:

- 1) The interests of the group or targets are contained in the contents of the policy so that the implementation runs to satisfy most parties so that implementation can work even though it is not possible to meet all the needs of the actors.
- 2) The benefits received are closely related to "who gets what" so that the solutions provided can provide benefits for the implementor and the subject of policy implementation.
- 3) Human resources, in this case, the Ministry of Transportation as the implementor of the terminal operating policy can act decisively (sanctions) if in the implementation of finding problems related to non-compliance with terminal operating policies.
- 4) A mental revolution needs to be carried out on the importance of operating type A km 17 Gambut Barakat terminal so that the level of compliance is high and there is no refusal to move.
- 5) Enforcement efforts, in this case, the prosecution in the event of a violation needs to be done, curbing needs to be carried out with joint operations of the Ministry of Transportation, the Provincial Transportation Agency, the Banjar District Transportation Agency, the Civil Service Police Unit and the Traffic Police.
- 6) Provision of sanctions by regulations regarding written warnings, administrative fines, suspension of licenses and/or revocation of licenses.

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